

FINANCIAL DEEPENING AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Godwin E. Bassey, Ph.D

Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Uyo, Uyo
godwinbassey07@yahoo.com

and

Ubong E. Effiong

Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences,
University of Uyo, Uyo
ubongeffiong3@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper examined the relationship between financial development and economic development in Nigeria using annual time series between 1981 and 2018. Financial development was captured with financial deepening indicator measured as a ratio of credit to the private sector to gross domestic product (GDP). The data were obtained from the 2018 Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. The study employed an econometric approach by incorporating granger causality test, unit root test, Bounds test, and the error correction mechanism. Findings from the Granger causality test revealed that there exists a unidirectional causality that flows from financial development to economic development in Nigeria, implying that the supply-leading finance hypothesis was prevalent. Also, there exist both a short-run and long-run positive and significant relationship between financial development (measured as a ratio of credit to private sector to GDP) and economic growth in Nigeria within the study period. It is in this light that the paper recommended that there is need for more financial market development that favours more credit to the private sector in order to stimulate economic growth. This can be achieved through strengthening the micro finance sector so as to make credits available and accessible to the micro entrepreneurs who are often deprived of credit by the conventional credit markets.

Keywords: Finance-led Growth, Financial System, Granger Causality Test, Error Correction Mechanism, Credit to private sector.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the 1990s, several studies were conducted to examine the theory on the relationship between the financial deepening and the real sector of the economy. Such include the works of King and Levine (1993), and Levine (1997). Using correlation analysis, their studies revealed that the financial sector has a

significant role to play in the development of the real sector of the economy. The role of the financial sector has also been described to include promoting savings (Bencivenga and Smith, 1991), providing vital information (Greenwood and Jovanovic, 1990), and affecting credit rationing (Boyd and Smith, 1997). The financial system has been described as an engine of growth in that as the financial sector extends credit to the productive sectors of the economy at affordable costs, the overall economy grows inclusively (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017). As noted by Beck and Levine (2004), financial institutions (banking system and financial market) can only improve the output growth of an economy if there are functional industrial activities, free flow of information, low transaction cost and an optimal resource allocation.

Prior to 1986, the Nigerian financial system was under “financial repression” with an undesirable real interest rate, a high tax burden on financial earnings, high liquidity, possible financial misallocations, and a high reserve requirement ratios (CBN,2003). After 1986, the financial markets became an active part of the economy. The lifting of repressive controls on financial market instruments was realized gradually over 1986 and beyond as part of policy change. It was expected that the 1986 shift in policy stance in the form of Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) would be a watershed in the life of the national economy (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017).

There have been diverse views on the linkages between the financial sector development and the real sector development of the economy. In this regards, the supply-leading finance, demand-following finance, the feedback hypothesis, the neutral hypothesis, and the structuralist hypothesis have been on the point of discussion over time. The supply-leading finance was propounded by Schumpeter (1911) and developed further by scholars such as Gurley and Shaw (1967), McKinnon (1973), and King and Levine (1993). These finance-led proponents are of the opinion that it is financial development that can propel economic growth due to improvement in the efficiency of capital accumulation or an increase in the rate of savings as well as the rate of investment. The demand-following finance took their tool by defining the direction of causality to flow from the real sector to the financial sector. To them, it is the improvements in the economy that drive higher demand for the use of money, which consequently promotes financial development (see Robinson, 1952; Goldsmith, 1969; Jung 1986; Lucas, 1988; and Kar and Pentecost,

Using the Nigerian data, evidence shows that financial development (measured here as a ratio of credit to the private sector to GDP) exhibits a positive relationship. This is presented in the Figure 1

Figure 1: Trend of Financial Development index and economic growth.

The credit to private sector as a ratio of GDP (CPS/GDP) and the log of gross domestic product (lnGDP) maintained an upward movement over time, though with some fluctuations in the part of CPS/GDP. However, lnGDP has maintained a steady upward growth over time. The key issue that arises from this positive nature of their relationship could be the direction of causality. That is, is it development in the financial sector that causes development in the real sector or the other way round?

There have been series of conflicting results on the relationship between financial development and real sector growth. The recent studies of Christopoulos and Tsionas (2004), Odeniran and Udejaja (2012), Ebiringa and Duruibe (2015), and Karimo and Ogbonna (2017) revealed that it is development in the financial sector that causes growth in the real sector. On the contrary, Madichie, et al. (2014) established that it is the development in the real sector that causes the development in the financial sector, while Osuji and Chigbu (2009) established a bidirectional causality between financial development and economic growth. The absence of any form of causality between the financial sector and the real sector was also noticed (Adekunle, Salami and Adedipe, 2013). These mixed findings and contentions in the direction of causality between financial development and real sector development are the major propeller of this study. This study therefore aims at examining the nature of the relationship between financial development and real sector development as well as examining the existence of a long-run relationship between the two sectors of the Nigerian economy.

The paper is structured in five sections. Following this introduction is section 2 which is the literature review. Section 3 deals with the methodology of the research, while section 4 presents the empirical findings. Finally, section 5 presents the conclusion and the recommendations of the study.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Underpinnings

The linkages between the financial sector and real sector of an economy has been discussed under five broad hypotheses – the supply-leading finance hypothesis, the demand-following finance hypothesis, the neutral hypothesis, the feedback hypothesis, and the structuralist hypothesis. The supply-leading finance advocates are of the opinion that it is development in the financial sector that leads to development in the real sector. The supply of investment finance is believed to stimulate growth in the real sector of the economy. Key proponent of the supply-leading hypothesis is Schumpeter (1911) and the idea is supported by scholars such as Calderon and Liu (2003), Gurley and Shaw (1967), King and Levine (1993), and McKinnon (1973). The crux of the matter here is that financial development has a positive effect on economic growth, and that the effect runs from financial development to economic growth which is caused by an improvement in the efficiency of capital accumulation or an increase in the rate of savings as well as the rate of investment. The transmission mechanism is that as entrepreneurs have new access to the supply-leading funds, their expectations increase and new horizons (or possible alternatives) are opened up, thereby making the entrepreneur “think big” (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017).

The demand-following finance hypothesis asserts that it is development in the real sector that triggers financial development. Among the key proponents of the hypothesis are Goldsmith (1969), Jung (1986), Kar and Pentecost (2000), Lucas (1988), Ndlovu (2013), Omotor (2007), and Robinson (1952), who are of the opinion that causality runs from economic growth to financial development. That is to say, an increase in economic growth causes a rise in demand for financial services and this result in the expansion of the financial sector. In their view, it is the improvements in the economy that drive higher demand for the use of money, which consequently promotes financial development. That is, financial markets develop and progress as a result of increased demand for their services from the growing real sector (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017). The development in the real sector can be achieved, based on the Keynesian theory, through an expansionary fiscal policy which increases aggregate demand and income, thereby raising demand for money. Thus, the Keynesians view is that financial deepening occurs as a result of an increase in government expenditure.

Scholars such as Apergis and Levine (2007) who are proponents of the neutral hypothesis assert that there is no relationship between financial development and economic growth, while the feedback hypothesis stipulates that there is a mutual effect between financial development and economic growth (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017).

However, the structuralist hypothesis is of the opinion that the causal relationship between financial development and economic growth is a function of the stage of economic development. At the early stage of development, the supply-leading finance becomes necessary since the development of new financial services creates new opportunities for savers and investors and causes an increase in economic growth. The implication of this is that at the early stage of economic development, financial development is necessary for economic development as it will stimulate real capital formation (Karimo and Ogbonna, 2017). As the economy and financial development soars, the supply-leading finance becomes less important and the demand-following finance sets into motion. The implication here is that economies at the early stage of development need to adopt the supply-leading finance, but as the economy grows over time, the demand-following finance becomes prominent.

This paper is therefore built on the foundation of the supply-leading finance and the demand-following finance hypothesis.

2.2 EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

There have been strands of empirical literature on financial development and economic development. Christopoulos and Tsionas (2004) using panel unit root test and panel cointegration analysis to examine the relationship between financial development and Economic growth in ten developing countries find strong evidence in favour of the hypothesis that long-run causality runs from financial development to growth and there is no evidence of bi-directional causality. Furthermore, they find a unique co integrating vector between growth and financial development and emphasize the long-run nature of the relationship between finance and growth.

Agu and Chukwu (2008) employed the augmented granger causality test approach developed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995) to ascertain the direction of causality between bank based financial deepening variables and economic growth in Nigeria between 1970 and 2005. Their study revealed that financial deepening and economic growth are positively correlated with one cointegrating vector indicating a stable and sustainable long run relationship. Their findings also suggested that the choice of bank based financial deepening variables influences the causality outcome. While variables like private sector credit, broad money supported the demand following hypothesis variables like loan deposit ratio and bank deposit liabilities were in favour of the supply leading hypothesis.

Osuji and Chigbu (2009) investigated the impact of financial development on economic growth in Nigeria, using time series data for the period 1960-2008. The research utilized co-integration analysis, causality test and error correction mechanism for analysis of the data. The results showed that money supply and

credit to private sector positively impacted on economic growth in Nigeria and were as well co-integrated with GDP for the study period. The Granger test shows a bi-directional causality existing between GDP and all the explanatory variables.

Odeniran and Udejaja (2012) used the Granger causality tests in a variance autoregressive framework to verify the competing finance-growth nexus hypothesis between the periods 1960 – 2009. The study reported that all the financial development indicators granger-cause output growth. However, growth does not granger-cause all the financial development indicators. Thus, net domestic credit and credit to private sector are equally driven by growth in output, thus indicating bi-directional causality for the indicators. The result from the variance decomposition reports that shock to deposit does not significantly affect net domestic credit, implying that the share of deposit liability in the total variations of net domestic credit is negligible.

Adekunle, Salami and Adedipe (2013) found evidence that there is no significant relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria using the ordinary least square (OLS) method. The study concluded that the link between financial and real sector still remains weak and could not propel the needed growth towards vision 2020.

Also, Audu and Okumoko (2013) re-established the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria within the periods 1970 – 2012. The study employed the long-run parsimonious error correction model to establish the links. The co-integration result reported the existence of a long-run relationship between financial development and economic growth. The commercial bank credit to private sector was observed to exert a positive and significant impact on economic growth. Contrary, the commercial bank credit to non-financial private firm has indirect impact on economic growth in the Nigerian economy. It was also observed that the ratio of commercial bank deposit to gross domestic product had a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Madichie, et al. (2014) empirically investigated the impact of financial development on economic growth in Nigeria during the period 1986 – 2012. The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) techniques, Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, error correction technique, and the Granger causality test were the methods employed in the study. Their findings revealed that financial development affects economic growth negatively in the long-run but positively in the short-run. Also, evidence of long-run relationship was established in the study. The granger causality test showed that causality runs from economic growth to financial development and not the other way round. They recommended that the government should device a means to energize the

micro finance sector so as to make credits available and accessible to micro entrepreneurs who are often deprived of credits by the conventional credit markets. This will help boost the private sector development and investment which is the engine of growth.

Mba (2015) investigated the impact of financial liberalization on economic growth in Nigeria between the periods of 1986 and 2011 using long-run estimates from Ordinary Least Square method. Using credit to private sector as a ratio of GDP to proxy financial liberalization, the findings showed that financial liberalization has negative impact on output growth in Nigeria. The author argued that the credits to private sector have not been used for productive activities which could have increased output but rather for buying and selling of consumables. The co-integration result reveals a long run relationship among the variables. The study advocates for change in the lending priority of the commercial bank to lend money to genuine private investors and not to the government and influential borrowers.

Similarly, Ebiringa and Duruibe (2015) adopted the vector autoregressive model to analyse the relationship between financial system development and economic growth in Nigeria. The empirical results revealed that there is no long run causality from financial system development indicators to growth. In the short-run, the effect of financial development on economic growth was positive. The study suggested that the financial system needed further deepening by offering innovative financial products and services and sound monetary policy formulation and implementation in order to adequately support short and long-term growth.

Iheanacho (2016) empirically examined the relationship between financial intermediary development and economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1981–2011 using the auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) approach to co-integration analysis. The results showed that the relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria is found to be insignificantly negative in the long-run and significantly negative in the short-run. The results highlighted the dominant role of the oil sector in economic activities in Nigeria. The study recommended strengthening the intermediary role of financial system in Nigerian economy by building institutional framework that would channel financial resources in the economy to productive investment projects through the financial system could stimulate economic activities in the private sector, lessen the burden on the public sector and the dominance of the oil sector in the economy.

Karimo and Ogbonna (2017) examined the direction of causality between financial deepening and economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1970 – 2013. The study adopted the Toda–Yamamoto augmented Granger causality test and results showed that the growth-financial deepening nexus in Nigeria follows the supply-leading hypothesis. The study recommended that policy efforts should be geared towards removing obstacles that undermine the growth of credit to the private sector, and must restore investors' confidence in the stock market operations.

Osisanwo (2017) examined the impact of financial development on economic growth in Nigeria using annual time series data between 1980 and 2014.

The study tests for the unit root and co-integration to determine the time series properties of the variables before using ordinary least square estimation technique to evaluate the long-run estimates. The results show that all the indicators of financial development except private sector credit ratio have positive impact on the economic growth in Nigeria. Thus, the study suggests that for the country to experience finance-led growth, the apex bank must ensure that loans are available to local industrial investors at a low interest rate.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Basic Research Design

This paper adopted secondary research and employed data from secondary sources for the period ranging from 1981 to 2018. The data were subjected to diagnostic test and multiple regression analysis was employed. Further, post diagnostic test was conducted to ascertain the stability of the obtained result.

3.2 Model Specification

The model for this study is specified based on the set objectives of the study.

Objective 1: To examine the nature of the causal relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria, the Granger causality test model is specified as follows:

$$GDP_t = s \sum_{i=1}^n \pi_i FIND_{t-i} + s \sum_{j=1}^n \beta_j GDP_{t-j} + \mu_{1t} \quad (1a)$$

$$FIND_t = s \sum_{i=1}^n \theta_i GDP_{t-i} + s \sum_{j=1}^n \lambda_j FIND_{t-j} + \mu_{2t} \quad (1b)$$

It is assumed that the disturbance terms μ_{1t} and μ_{2t} are uncorrelated.

Objective 2: To investigate the influence of financial development on economic development in Nigeria, the model is specified thus:

$$GDP = f(FIND, EXC, GEX, PLR) \quad (2a)$$

which in its estimable form, yields in the double log function,

$$\ln GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 FIND_t + \alpha_2 EXC_t + \alpha_3 \ln GEX_t + \alpha_4 PLR_t + \mu_t \quad (2b)$$

where α_0 = constant intercept term,

α_1 to α_4 = parameters,

μ_t = error term,

$\ln GDP_t$ = natural log gross domestic product (a measure for economic growth),

$FIND_t$ = financial development (measured as the ratio of credit to the private sector to GDP),

EXC_t = exchange rate,

$\ln GEX_t$ = natural log of total government expenditure, and

PLR_t = prime lending rate.

3.3 Apriori Expectations

It is expected that α_1

3.4 Data Source

Annual time series data used for this study covered the period 1981 to 2018. They were all obtained from the 2018 Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin. The choice of this period is to tie the effect of the period of financial regulation and that of financial liberalisation as experienced during the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP).

3.5 Analytical Approach

The analytical approach for this paper follows the Granger Causality Test, Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Bounds test for cointegration, and the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM). The diagnostic test for unit root is done based on the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test technique to ascertain the stationary process of the series. The general functional form for the test is given as

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \delta t + \varepsilon_t \quad (3a)$$

Where Y is a time series, t is a linear time trend, Δ is the first difference operator, Ψ_0 is a constant, i is the optimum number of lags in the independent variables, and ε_t is random error term.

The Granger Causality test follows the Pairwise Granger Causality Test to test for the direction of causality between variables. In the Granger causality test, the null hypothesis is that a variable does not Granger cause the other. In making inferences here, the F-statistic will be used and the 5% level of significance will be employed. The ARDL approach to the test for cointegration was done using the Bounds test. This is done to ascertain the existence of a long-run relationship between variables of interest. Cointegration is therefore found if regressing variables which are stationary at first difference, $I(1)$, yields a residual which is stationary at level, $I(0)$. As noted by (Madichie, et al., 2014),

The implication of this analysis is that deviation or drift may occur between the variables, but this is temporary as equilibrium holds in the long run for them. When the cointegration of these variables is confirmed, it portends that a non-spurious long run relationship exists. When this is combined with the error correction model (ECM), consistent estimates of both long run and short run coefficients is evident (Madichie, et al., 2014).

The error correction mechanism (ECM) shows how the short-run disequilibrium is corrected in the long-run. The ARDL error correction mechanism automatically estimate the ECM. In the manual way, the static OLS estimation is first carried out and the error terms are obtained and tested for the presence of unit root (in this case, the existence of cointegration). Upon rejection of the null hypothesis of no cointegration, the lagged residuals from the cointegration equation are imposed as the error correction term $ECM(-1)$ in an error correction equation. The ECM is specified as follows.

$D(\ln GDP) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D(\text{FIND}) + \alpha_2 D(\text{EXC}) + \alpha_3 D(\ln \text{GEX}) + \alpha_4 D(\text{PLR}) + ? \text{ECM}(-1) + \varepsilon$ (3b)
Where D is the difference operator; ECM(-1) is the vector of stationary residuals from the cointegration equation (2b); ? is the coefficient of error correction term measuring the speed of adjustment from one period to another; ε is a pure white noise error term.

4 EMPIRICAL FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The descriptive statistics for the variables are presented as follows.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Series

	lnGDP	FIND	EXC	lnGEX	PLR
Mean	8.534	14.203	88.666	6.015	17.577
Median	8.708	12.693	97.400	6.703	17.540
Maximum	11.758	21.307	306.190	8.903	29.800
Minimum	4.976	9.152	0.610	2.266	7.750
Std. Dev.	2.336	3.932	87.199	2.228	4.628
Skewness	-0.188	0.598	0.799	-0.426	0.204
Kurtosis	1.600	1.829	2.965	1.739	3.668
Sum	324.307	539.695	3369.303	228.576	667.912
Observations	38	38	38	38	38

Source: Author Computation

Table 1 indicates that the log of gross domestic product (lnGDP), financial deepening (FIND), exchange rate (EXC), log of total government expenditure (lnGEX), and prime lending rate (PLR) averaged 8.534, 14.203, 88.666, 6.015, and 17.577 respectively, with a standard deviation of 2.336, 3.932, 87.199, 2.228, and 4.628 respectively. LnGDP and lnGEX are skewed to the left while FIND, EXC, and PLR are all positively skewed. The sample size for each of the variables is given as 38.

4.2 Correlation Matrix

The degree of correlations between variables in the study is presented in the table below.

Table 2: Correlations Between Variables

	lnGDP	FIND	EXC	lnGEX	PLR
lnGDP	1.000				
FIND	0.807	1.000			
EXC	0.900	0.829	1.000		
lnGEX	0.992	0.768	0.871	1.000	
PLR	-0.185	-0.021	0.072	0.252	1.000

Source: Author Computation

There is strong positive correlation between FIND and lnGDP, EXC and lnGDP as well as that between lnGEX and lnGDP. This is represented by their respective correlations coefficient of 0.807, 0.900, and 0.992. A weak degree of negative correlation is observed between PLR and lnGDP as indicated by the correlation coefficient of 0.185. Each variable correlates perfectly with itself yielding the correlation coefficient of 1.000.

4.3 Static (Long-Run) Estimates

The long-run result of the estimates of the regression function is given as follows.

Table 3: Long-run OLS Result
Dependent variable: lnGDP

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
C	2.670***	0.248	10.765	0.0000
FIND	0.032*	0.017	1.896	0.0667
EXC	-0.002**	0.001	-2.346	0.0252
lnGEX	0.929***	0.037	25.376	0.0000
PLR	-0.022**	0.009	-2.540	0.0160

R-squared = 0.9923

Adjusted R-squared = 0.9913

F-statistic = 1057.511***

Durbin -Watson statistic = 1.499

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

*Note: ***, **, and * denotes significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.*

The result from Table 3 indicate that FIND and lnGEX posed a positive and significant influence on lnGDP at 10% and 1% level respectively. They also satisfy the a priori expectations to be positive. This implies that for a unit percentage increase in financial deepening and log of total government expenditure, the log of GDP (economic growth) increases by 0.032% and 0.929% respectively. Exchange rate (EXC) and prime lending rate (PLR) is also observed to exhibit a negative and significant impact on economic growth at the 5% level of significance. This implies that for a unit percentage increase in exchange rate and prime lending rate, economic growth declines by 0.002% and 0.022% respectively. The constant term (2.670) which is statistically significant at the 1% level implies that the log of GDP will be 2.670 if every variable in the model is held constant at zero.

The coefficient of determination (R-squared) which is 0.9923 measures the goodness of fit of the regression line. This value implies that the explanatory variables explain 99.23% of the total variations in the dependent variable. The value still remains high after adjusting for the degree of freedom (i.e. 99.13%).

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.499 clearly shows that there is a clear absence of serial correlation in the model, while the F-statistic which is significant at the 1% level indicates that the overall model is significant.

4.4 Post-Diagnostic Test

The post-diagnostic test here includes the serial correlation test, Heteroscedasticity test, and Ramsey RESET test.

F-statistic	1.641	Prob. F(2,31)	0.2102
Obs*R-squared	3.637	Prob. Chi-Square (2)	0.1623

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

Since the F-statistic is not statistically significant at the 5% level as indicated by the p-value of 0.2102, the null hypothesis of serial correlation is therefore rejected. Hence, our error terms are not correlated with each other. This can be seen from Table 3 where the Durbin-Watson statistic is 1.499.

Table 5: Heteroscedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.500508	Prob. F(4,33)	0.7355
Obs*R-squared	2.173510	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.7039
Scaled explained SS	2.560046	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.6339

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

The F-statistic and the Chi-square are not statistically significant at the 5% level. Hence, the null hypothesis of heteroscedasticity is rejected. Therefore,

there is homoscedasticity implying a constant variance.

Table 6: Ramsey RESET Test

Specification: LNGDP C FIND EXC LNGEX PLR

Omitted Variables: Squares of fitted values

	Value	Degree of freedom	Probability
t-statistic	3.915725	32	0.0004
F-statistic	15.33290	(1, 32)	0.0004
Likelihood ratio	14.87585	1	0.0001

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

Table 6 revealed that the t-statistic (3.916), F-statistic (15.333), and the Likelihood ratio (14.876) are statistically significant at the 1% level as indicated by their respective p-value of 0.0004, 0.0004, and 0.0001. Hence, the null hypothesis that the model is wrongly specified is rejected. Another implication here is that our data fit into the model that was specified for the study.

4.5 Stability Test

The Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of squares serves as the stability test. This is represented in the figure below.

Figure 2: Stability Test for the Long-Run Estimates

As shown in Figure 2, the Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) of Squares line is within the 5% critical value bounds. Therefore, the estimates of the long-run model is stable.

4.6 Granger Causality Test

In identifying the direction of causality between financial development and economic development, the Granger causality test result is presented below.

Table 7: Pairwise Granger Causality Test
Number of lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Observations	F-Statistic	Prob.
FIND does not Granger Cause lnGDP	36	3.6285	0.0384
lnGDP does not Granger Cause FIND		3.2128	0.0540
EXC does not Granger Cause lnGDP	36	0.8305	0.4453
lnGDP does not Granger Cause EXC		3.5413	0.0412
lnGEX does not Granger Cause lnGDP	36	4.7189	0.0163
lnGDP does not Granger Cause lnGEX		4.0050	0.0284
PLR does not Granger Cause lnGDP	36	2.5806	0.0919
lnGDP does not Granger Cause PLR		0.4486	0.6426

Source: Extract from Author Computation using Eviews 10.

The Granger causality test result in Table 7 shows that at 5% level, there exist a one-way causality flowing from financial development (FIND) to economic growth (lnGDP). This is indicated by the F-statistic of 3.62850 and the p-value of 0.0384 hence, financial development Granger causes real sector development in Nigeria. Similarly, there exist a unidirectional causality flowing from lnGDP to EXC. This implies that economic growth causes exchange rate and not the other way around. A bi-directional causality flows between lnGEX and lnGDP. This implies that economic growth causes total government expenditure and total government expenditure in turn causes economic growth. This is shown by their respective p-values of 0.0163 and 0.0284 respectively. At the 5% level of significance, there is no causality between prime lending rate (PLR) and economic growth (lnGDP) as indicated by their respective p-value of 0.0919 and 0.6426, but at 10% level of significance, PLR ganger causes lnGDP.

4.7 Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dicky-Fuller unit root test result is presented below. All the test follows the constant–linear trend assumption.

Table 8: Augmented Dickey-Fuller Unit Root Test Result

Variable	Level	Probability	First Difference	Probability	Order of Integration
lnGDP	-0.14506	0.9920	-3.7885	0.0421	I(1)
FIND	-2.3750	0.3858	-5.5662	0.0003	I(1)
EXC	-1.9434	0.6114	-4.5470	0.0046	I(1)
lnGEX	-0.2944	0.9878	-7.5132	0.0000	I(1)
PLR	-5.0688	0.0014	-6.1989	0.0001	I(0)

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

Table 8 indicates that lnGDP, FIND, EXC, and lnGEX are all stationary at first difference, I(1), while prime lending rate (PLR) is stationary at level. This mixed order of I(0) and I(1) variables warrants the use of the Bounds test to test for the existence of a long-run relationship.

4.8 Bounds Test for Long-Run Relationship

The Bounds test for the existence of the long-run relationship is presented below.

Table 9: Bounds Test Result

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic	28.84655	10%	2.2	3.09
K	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

Since the F-statistic (28.84655) is far more greater than the upper I(0) and lower bounds I(1), the null hypothesis of no levels relationship is rejected. Hence, there exist a long-run between the dependent variable and explanatory variables. The short-run model is therefore estimated.

4.9 Error Correction Mechanism

The result of the error correction mechanism is presented in table 12 below.

Table 10: Short-Run Error Correction Mechanism

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(FIND)	0.019***	0.006	3.167	0.0056
D(EXC)	-0.001*	0.001	-1.879	0.0730
D(LNGEX)	0.015	0.059	0.249	0.8057
D(PLR)	0.005**	0.003	1.713	0.0102
D(PLR(-1))	-0.010***	0.003	-3.232	0.0037
D(PLR(-2))	-0.012***	0.003	-3.899	0.0007
ECM(-1)	-0.168***	0.012	-14.516	0.0000

R-squared = 0.7653

Adjusted R -squared = 0.7150

Durbin-Watson Statistic = 1.686

AIC = -2.739

Source: Author Computation using Eviews 10.

Note: ***, **, and * denotes significance at 1%, 5%, and 10% respectively.

In the short-run, all the variables retain their a priori signs except prime lending rate. Here, changes in financial deepening (D(FIND)) and changes in interest rate (D(PLR)) exert a positive and significant effect on the changes in economic growth (D(lnGDP)) at the 5% level of significance. Thus for a unit percentage increase in changes in financial deepening and changes in interest rate, economic growth increased by 0.019% and 0.005% respectively. Also, changes in the log of government expenditure (D(lnGEX)) positively influences changes in economic growth but such effect is seen to be statistically insignificant as shown by the p-value of 0.8057. Similarly, changes in exchange rate (D(EXC)) negatively and significantly influences changes in economic growth at the 10% level of significance. Therefore, for a unit percentage change in D(EXC), lnGDP decreased by 0.001%. The lagged values of the changes in prime lending rate (D(PLR(-1)) and D(PLR(-2))) exert negative and significant impact on D(lnGDP) at the 5% level.

Most importantly, the ECM(-1) term is rightly signed (negative) and statistically significant at the 1% level of significance. It measures the speed of adjustment toward equilibrium in the long-run. The ECM(-1) coefficient (-0.168) indicates that about 16.8% of this disequilibrium in the economy is corrected annually. In other words, almost 16.8% of the equilibrium of the previous year's

shock is adjusted back to the long-run equilibrium in the current year. However, the speed of adjustment is quite slow.

4.10 Major Findings and Discussion of Findings

The major findings of this research work are:

- i. It is development in the financial sector that causes development in the real sector. The Granger causality test indicated that financial development Granger causes economic development hence, the findings lends support to the supply-following finance hypothesis. The implication here is that the financial system needs to play a pivotal role in the growth process of the country.
- ii. financial deepening positively and significantly influences economic growth both in the short-run and in the long-run. The implication here is that finance-led growth hypothesis is valid in Nigeria both in the short run and in the long-run.
- iii. Prime lending rate positively influences economic growth in the short-run but negatively do so in the long-run. This implies that in the short-run, investors may not really be mindful of the rate of interest when their focus is to start up. However, in the long-run they may be very cautious since they can rely on their retained earnings for expansion.

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study investigated the influence of financial development on economic growth in Nigeria for the period 1981 to 2018. The role of the financial system is crucial for economic development of a country as it promote savings (Bencivenga and Smith, 1991), provide vital information (Greenwood and Jovanovic, 1990), and affect credit rationing (Boyd and Smith, 1997). The direction of causality between financial development and economic growth has been established on the basis of the supply-leading and demand-following finance hypotheses. Financial development has also been discussed to be a function of the level of economic development of a country based on the structuralist hypothesis. Findings from the study has established that the prevalent finance-growth hypothesis in Nigeria is supply-leading, implying that development in the financial sector is what propels growth in the real sector of the Nigerian economy. This indicates that, based on the structuralist hypothesis, Nigeria is still at her early stage of development and therefore needs supply of investment finance in order to stimulate growth in the real sector of the economy. Also, the study revealed that financial development posed a positive and significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria within the study period.

Based on the finding of this study, the following recommendations are submitted.

1. Since it is observed that there is a causal relationship between financial development and economic growth in Nigeria, concerted efforts should be geared towards innovative financial system that will be able to stand

- the demands of the real sector in terms of investment finance.
2. Also, since there is a positive and significant relationship between financial development and economic growth, there is need for more financial market development that favours more credit to the private sector in order to stimulate economic growth. This can be achieved through strengthening the micro finance sector so as to make credits available and accessible to the micro entrepreneurs who are often deprived of credit by the conventional credit markets.
 3. The government should encourage monetary authorities like the Central Bank of Nigeria to build a conducive and enabling environment for friendly interest rates so that prospective investors can increase their investment and raise the nation's production capacity.

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